
Contractual recruitment through the lens of the variable motivation of Moroccan teachers.

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Abstract

The recent and emblematic phenomenon of contractualisation and regionalisation of resources in the education sector in Morocco, leads us to question the influential effects of this change on the behavioural paradigm of teaching staff and, above all, their motivations.

In this study empirically, a mixed study was conducted in the Fes Meknes region, using a questionnaire administered to 215 contract teachers, selected at random.

The objective is to investigate and better understand the different parameters analysed and to evaluate their experience. The data were analysed using SPSS according to an analytical approach. The results based on the data collected enabled us to propose a conceptual framework of the main variables explaining the phenomenon of demotivation, feelings of inequality and insecurity among most teachers, particularly in relation to contract recruitment, and to address the various parameters necessary to resolve these issues.

Our findings confirm that there is a significant correlation between recruitment methods and employee motivation.

A large number of teachers viewed this as a source of demotivation and discrimination, and year after year they have continued to demand their integration into the civil service, as evidenced by repeated strikes, absenteeism, insubordination, abandonment of posts, and boycotts of staff meetings.

The survey results indicate that, in the minds of teachers, the employment relationship is structured around a predefined framework; the temporary nature of their employment appears to contradict their explicit, specific expectations, which are driven more by relational than transactional logic, and where issues related to job security take on particular significance.

Key words: Contractualisation, motivation, RH and comportement organisationnel, organisational change, status, teacher.

1. Introduction

Faced with an ongoing quest for new management methods, Morocco is employing one of the most important and innovative measures of this decade: the contractualization and regionalisation of teachers, at a time when statutory recruitment was the principle in the civil service and status was the basis of a professional relationship with precisely defined ground rules: "conditions of access (age, diploma, entrance examination), remuneration (indices and points), geographical mobility and professional advancement (internal competitions, transfers)". (**Mauri Majos, 2009**) Nevertheless, due to a lack of measurable, effective and satisfactory results, and the gradual clash with automatic and systematic career and salary advancement without clear and corollary performance, excessive and sometimes unconditional protection, and too many and inefficient civil servants, contract recruitment (**Pons, 2021**) has become a genuine alternative to the linear career, which is tending to disappear, giving rise to a wide variety of professional relationships.

It should be noted that the contractual recruitment of teachers in Morocco is an education policy implemented since 2016 by the Ministry of National Education as part of the reform of the civil service and the decentralisation of the education system, and adjusted since 2024 through regional recruitment.

More than 157,000 contract teachers through the Regional Academies of Education and Training (AREF), which is equivalent to the total number of hires over 20 years, or 32% of all budget posts created and of the Ministry's current civil servant workforce of 287,092 (51% of the civilian total). Since then, it has become the recruitment method par excellence, both for managing Morocco's school system and for controlling the State's direct wage bill, which represents over 11% of GDP. This recruitment drive is set to intensify over the coming years, and this will lead to serious changes in HRM, not all of which are taking place under the best of conditions, notably strong opposition and reluctance on the part of those involved. Indeed, since its adoption, debates on its results - ranging from outright disapproval to tempered enthusiasm - have been divergent, with many questions raised about its effects on the quality of teaching.

It is for these reasons that the present research aims to answer the following question: What is the impact of status following the policy of contractualization and regionalisation of resources on the motivation of contract teachers?

In Morocco, few experimental studies have really examined the effect of status on teacher motivation. This aspect seems necessary and may in fact testify to the success or failure of the organization, as the players are not necessarily inclined to accept it (with all that the civil service represents in Moroccan culture) and may develop active or passive resistance to the integration of

this new process, which represents a disruption, a fear of losing a known existing for an uncertain future, a loss of stability and an attack on identity.

In order to contribute to a very topical and worrying issue, and to show that it is enough to look at more qualitative variables to have a considerable effect on the agent's behavior, leading to its integration and evaluation, our hypothesis could be put forward as follows:

-Hypothesis: The new status adopted significantly influences teacher's motivation.

This research is structured in three parts. Firstly, we will present the conceptual challenge represented by a literature review of the main concepts related to our subject. Secondly, we will address the methodological challenge of collecting and analyzing the data, and the third point will be devoted to presenting the results and the pragmatic challenge (psychological contract versus current trends).

2-THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The objective of this article is perfectly in line with the theoretical definition of the characteristics of the motivational factors on which the employment relationship is based (**Abraham, 1998**). Motivation in the present work concerns the contractual recruitment of teachers.

In order to gain a better understanding of this so-called contractual employment relationship (**Berthet, 2011**), we have drawn on the theoretical foundations and approaches that enable us to grasp the behavioral paradigm, and the coordination mechanisms derived from both psychological contract theory and equity theory, and their contributions to the logic of contractualization.

Recruitment by contract is a procedure granted to the employer to provide greater reactivity and management flexibility, and represents a means of circumventing the difficulties that statutory recruitment can entail. It is fully in line with the need to rationalize the planning, regulation, control and evaluation of human resources management and public spending (**Emery, Y et Giauque (2012)**, to enhance the quality of services provided to users, and to respond to the changing demands of society.

2-1 The Theory of the Psychological Contract.

Given that any relationship between two parties is essentially based on an exchange relationship, The Psychological Contract as a theory studies the interactions between the individual and the organization, analyzed on the basis of individual perceptions of the obligations existing between the agent and his employer, tacit and psychological elements, which cannot be presented in a long-term employment relationship.

The employment relationship (**Baudry, 2008**) then revolves around a predefined schema guiding the employee's attitude and behavior, where the idea of a career seems to take shape in the form of explicit, specific expectations, responding more to a relational than a transactional logic, the

determinants of this relationship in the Moroccan context, and the necessary adjustments, will be analyzed from the perspective of the contributions of the concept of the psychological contract, based mainly on the contributions of Rousseau and (**Guerrero, 2004**) to be able to verify the veracity of data concerning an entity at a given time.

However, in this exchange, not all needs can be satisfied, just as not all desires can be fulfilled. This is how the principle of organizational change and reality comes into play. While human beings seek to relieve their tensions by satisfying their needs, the reality principle takes external demands into account in order to dismiss, postpone, abandon or even change one's motivations so as to enable a better relationship with the world, and sometimes with one's colleagues.

In this context, the CP becomes the driving force behind motivation in working relationships, a valuable and effective management tool designed to act preventively to readjust when people decide to bind themselves together through reciprocal obligations and interdependencies that they voluntarily accept in order to achieve common goals.

In this sense, "the organization's behavior is the equilibrium behavior of a complex contractual system made up of maximizing agents with different and conflicting objectives". The solution to this problem of divergent interests between the main agent, the "organization", and the agent, the "teacher", is to set up a management control system that enables individuals to commit to the organization.

This commitment can be more complex, as it is less mechanical, hence the interest of this theory in describing commitment and disengagement behaviours, which is at the heart of the "contract" philosophy.

The definition of the psychological contract involves the following three points: Reciprocity and exchange in the employment relationship between the actors in the psychological contract, types of motivation (intrinsic, extrinsic) and their effects on the organization's actions.

2-2 Equity Theory

Generally speaking, equity theory in the literature first appeared in 1963, when psychologist John Stacey Adams identified the notion of equity within an organization as a source of motivation for employees (Shilpa, Shinde (2025), This relationship presents a limited level of attachment and investment in organizations when the agent within the school system compares his or her contractual situation with those of the statuaries, (a reference point) this comparison can modulate the affective organizational commitment of these workers.

A guiding idea of equity theory (Kellerhals, 1988) is that agents' perception of a situation or solution as inequitable leads them to adopt behaviors that increase transaction costs and have a non-negligible impact on performance (**Ramboarison-Lalao, 2019**).

This situation constitutes a pivotal period marked by a radical change for young teachers faced with a drastic drop in motivation and low social attractiveness, the absence of tenure in the civil service and therefore the questioning of career and retirement plans. This suggests that this choice is not only the result of rational processes, but also of partly unconscious social processes. **(Moniolle, C. (2020).**

Any individual will only engage in an activity when he or she is convinced that it takes into account the resolution of his or her essential needs. Obviously, during a process of organizational change, the study of the behavior of individuals, and in particular the teaching staff - the most significant resource and the main determinant - involves several elements bringing perceptions and interactions into play.

We begin by examining the motivations to teach of individuals whose initial professional career is teaching. Within this framework, we describe the various dimensions of this motivation, qualitative and quantitative, highlighted in the Moroccan context **(Maia, V., Raymondie, R.-A. et Steiner, D.-D. (2024).** We then present the effects of recruitment on the various motivations using a recent theoretical model that could help guide research on the subject, as well as the results of studies based on this model.

To meet the needs of this research, it is therefore useful to know the perception of these actors and their interactions, which differ widely when we refer to the two theories we have seen on the theoretical level.

In the case of adverse selection, it's rather people who don't have the aptitude for teaching who become teachers, and the best candidates, aware of the difficulty of the job, or with the disposition of superior skills, will seek other alternatives and succeed in stabilizing themselves in more remunerative jobs.

There is also organizational commitment, which in the literature is generally considered to be the emotional bond that individuals build with an organization on the basis of shared professional and ethical values, increasing their desire to remain members and contribute to the smooth running of the organization (Paillé, 2005).

This conceptualization of organizational commitment as an affective construct is complemented by two other proposed concepts such as motivation (need construct) and perceived change (moral construct), respectively (Meyer, Allen & Smith, 1993; Meyer & Allen, 1991). Once again, in line with the understanding of the psychological contract as a social construct, it should be noted that each of these dependent variable dimensions is linked to individuals' dynamic and contextual perceptions of their relationship with the organization.

The motivating role of status is important, as it helps to identify intrinsic and extrinsic elements and to guide the manager towards the most efficient system (statutory or contractual) (Barraud, 2014).

3-THE METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Starting from a positivist epistemological choice, through the adoption of a mixed methodology (AISSA, 2001) based on an exploratory phase adopting a qualitative method which enabled us to elaborate and agree on the list of constructs to be mobilized and to develop the research model, and an exploratory phase based on a quantitative method in which we will use questionnaires and semi-directed interviews addressed to teachers as data collection tools. We have opted for an abductive approach, which takes empirical observations as a starting point and allows us to make empirically verifiable conjectures, organized from March to June 2022.

Our epistemological and methodological choices are guided by our research object and research question, rejecting any default assumptions. It is for this reason that we have adopted an immersive approach to social reality, which allows us to understand the motivations and issues that the actors within it articulate.

We conducted a systematic analysis of primary documents and various sources; all existing sources were examined, classified, and meticulously analyzed:

1-The official administrative data (statutes, circulars, decrees, ministerial memos, school statistics, demographic data, etc.)

2-A literature review compiling secondary data on education and macroeconomic statistics, as well as national laws on teacher management; strategies and planning developed around this specific profession. Among the documents consulted are contracts[1]. The semi-directed interviews were conducted using structured discussion guides organized around the themes and questions of our research to foster primarily verbal interaction, since the data collected “first informs us about the speaker’s thoughts and secondarily about the reality that is the subject of the discourse.”

The questionnaire was administered online (80% via email). We were able to collect 215 responses to the questionnaire designed for teachers. The collected data were examined from a descriptive and analytical perspective using graphs, charts, and frequency circles to verify the quality and completeness of the information (Ben Aissa, H., 2001). We removed incomplete responses. The data were recoded when necessary and then transformed into variables that were easier to present and analyze using SPSS software, which allowed us to analyze the statistics for all variables and test the relationships.

See figure 1. Analysis of **Motivational process of the contract recruitment system**

Figure 1: Motivational process of the contract recruitment system

Source: compiled by us.

3.1 Population and sample

More specifically, the study focused on 215 contract teachers who constituted our target population, a representative sample of teachers in each provincial directorate among the nine AREF Fès Meknès of Morocco directorates working in all three cycles (primary, college and qualifying) and in both environments (rural & urban).

The breakdown of respondents by marital status reveals that 52% of our sample are married, while 44% are single, and by gender reveals a slight predominance of the male sex, with 53% of respondents being male against 47% female.

As for the professional side, our sample includes 57% primary school teachers, followed by 28% secondary school teachers and 15% secondary school teachers. We note a predominance of young people at 54%, aged 22 to 30, and followed by the 31 to 40 age group at 33%. This may be explained by the number of young people with higher diplomas entering the sector, and also the result of the ministry's career development and management plans.

With the aim of classifying the surveys according to their experience in the job, we have arranged them into five classes. We note that the category most present in our sample is that of managers with less than 5 years' seniority in the sector. This group accounts for 52% of the total. The second category, 28%, is made up of those who have worked in the sector for between 4 and 5 years.

In reading the results, we note that the level of education is divided entirely into two parts: graduates with only Bac+4 represent 50% of our sample, and individuals with Bac+5 amount to 31%. Those with a doctorate, however, represent only 6% of the sample.

According to our sample, scientific disciplines are the highest, accounting for 31%, followed by literary disciplines (26%) and economic and management sciences.

The 215 teachers are spread across the region's 9 provincial departments. The 4 provincial departments that responded most to the questionnaire were Fès and Taounate, followed by Séfrou and Moulay Yaccoub.

3.2 Data analysis

Data processing was carried out using SPSS, AMOS and NVIVO .

The first round of data collection consisted of semi-structured interviews. Teachers were asked to identify the perceptions they considered necessary when faced with this recruitment modality. They did so by describing it in general terms or by linking it to specific processes compared to their tenured colleagues.

This study, carried out at the Fès Meknès Regional Academy of Education and Training (Morocco), uses a questionnaire to understand and analyze the impact of the new recruitment methods introduced in recent years on the behavioral variable, and to determine the motivational position (intrinsic or extrinsic) of the respondents.

Through an empirical survey of a well-defined population of young teachers newly recruited by contract, it seems appropriate to study individuals' representation of the world of work, as well as their expectations within a framework of organizational change.

4-THE EMPIRICAL FRAMEWORK

Motivation is at the root of every movement, every behavior that drives us to act. It's a tension generated by the surge of psychic energy, an inner excitement and a will to give one's best, which appears, develops and fades with the addition of certain conditions. Its position in the choice of profession is very crucial for knowing the reasons that force teachers to opt for it. (Yenikoye, 2018)

The Ministry of Education's Strategic Vision 2015-2030 states that the candidate must be "motivated by the profession and have psychological, cognitive and ethical predispositions".

4.1 - types of teacher motivation

In scientific jargon, and in line with Kyriacou and Coulthard's theoretical model, motivations to become a teacher fall into three categories:

- Altruistic motivations: the search for important and useful work, the desire to help children succeed and also to improve society;
- intrinsic motivation: performing a task for the pleasure and satisfaction it brings, with an interest in the activity of teaching children, as well as in the mobilization of disciplinary skills. (Brousseau, 2001). This refers to the absence of material rewards or constraints. They are linked to the ontological characteristics of the profession;

- Extrinsic motivations: benefits not directly related to the professional activity itself (Kyriacou M. &., (2000).). These include pay, status and vacations.

Finally, the last category, known as amotivation (Louche, 2006), considers situations in which the individual establishes no relationship between his or her behaviour and the results he or she obtains. The individual is not motivated and finds himself or herself in a state of resignation and renunciation.

With these different types of motivation, we wonder about the attractiveness of the teaching profession in Morocco. Should we conclude that it is attractive, given the very high unemployment rate among young people with higher education qualifications (almost 28% for university graduates, according to the HCP)? All the more so as the level of requirements for entry into the profession remains very low compared to other professions.

This question on motivation was put to teachers in the following terms: Why did you choose teaching?

In Morocco, teacher recruitment competitions are very popular. For example, in December 2018, for the recruitment of 15,000 teachers, some 220,000 candidates applied and 149,000 of them were admitted to take the exam.

Examination of the results and data collected from this survey, which responded to our questionnaire, focused on several factors concerning motivation.

According to our survey, the main motivations for choosing the profession are mostly intrinsic, with 60% of respondents stating that they chose it out of love or vocation, or because of an interest in the profession.

The second most common reason given by the teachers surveyed (22%) was extrinsic, linked to rewards or the likelihood of securing a stable and sufficient income, and they stated that they had chosen this profession out of convenience, to be assured of a fixed salary and to protect themselves from unemployment and job insecurity.

In addition, 13% say that they didn't find a job because they had no other choice, and they were subjected to a single solution, by default, to escape unemployment. Last but not least, teachers (representing only 4% of the total) said that their work schedule (hours, vacations, part-time work, etc.) fitted in well with their responsibilities, making it possible to reconcile their private and professional lives, especially for women (Chart 1). Figure 2

Figure 2: Reasons for choosing the teaching profession

Source: compiled by us.

The second question asked at this level: When you're teaching, how do you feel? 64% of teachers said they were highly motivated, while 26% had an average level of motivation and 10% were not very motivated.

Figure 3: Level of motivation of contract teachers

Source: compiled by us.

The survey also shows that there are other intrinsic motivations, which generally represent a choice of profession due to a first professional experience in another field or after a period in private education. This new trend has been accelerated by the regionalization of recruitment via the AREF, in particular by the abolition or extension of the age limit for access to competitive examinations." The reasons for choosing the teaching profession "are generally external.

Despite this high rate, which exceeds 60%, the teachers questioned expressed their dissatisfaction with the feeling of inequity due to the difference in status compared to civil servant teachers, which plays a predominant and even catalyzing role in the majority of the teachers surveyed, especially after the transition from civil service to contractualization.

The status of teachers, which in the past was highly respected by public opinion, is leading to high levels of attrition and doubts about the long-term viability of this policy, especially from a management point of view.

The following graph confirms our analysis, with 74 academy teacher-facilitator responses citing a feeling of unfairness in the face of the difference in status compared to civil servant teachers, and job security as the primary source of stress in the system, followed by working conditions.

- Lack of teaching materials and working conditions
- Conflicting relations with superiors
- Job security
- Short-term vocational training
- Comparison with colleagues
- Feeling of inequity due to difference in status with civil servant teachers

Figure 4: Stress factors for contract teachers

Source: compiled by us.

Whereas for a long time, Moroccan culture favored membership of the civil service, often represented as the ideal type of career for an individual where a young student having proved his merits through the competitive examination would join a stable continuous career without great difficulty, and a professional milieu which is the object of economic and social privilege and benefits from guaranteed employment by making a regular and permanent "career".

This mutation has created a resistance to change, a powerful "stressor" that provokes a state of psychological imbalance in individuals, epitomized by repetitive strikes. We need to look at the causes. Some are linked to feelings of unfairness, while others are linked to job security in the face of a system that is considered contractual, i.e., part of a given timeframe. It would be seen as an obstacle that needs to be removed.

4.2- The effects of teacher motivation

The second section will attempt to weave the link between motivation and its effects on mode of employment, function and interests, and will again be the subject of a detailed analysis, but this time to better understand resistance to change. These effects are expressed at two levels: firstly, with a feeling of inequity, and secondly, through insecurity in the face of contractual employment.

4.2.1 Motivation in the face of unfairness and injustice.

According to equity theory, the driving force behind productivity is when each agent at work has a tendency to compare his or her situation (salary, benefits, status, workload, etc.) with that of other personnel within or outside the same organization, in order to accomplish the same mission. Social or organizational justice is another facet of the behavioral variable for contract teachers, playing a predominant and even catalyzing role in the majority of surveyed teachers' discourse, especially after the transition from civil service to contractualization.

In other words, contract teachers are no longer considered as civil servants, and the procedures defined in the existing statutes do not apply to them. This creates a clear sense of inequity in terms of professional development, disciplinary procedures and assessment, for example.

If the ratio between their efforts and their rewards is equivalent to that of other Rhs, they will be satisfied with their work. If not, the result will be dissatisfaction. Adaptation or regulation at work is linked to this sense of fairness, and satisfaction or dissatisfaction in this respect will be reflected in the Rhs' maintenance or change of their behaviours at work. (ADAMS, October 1963)

According to our study, professional status remains the element of comparison that establishes a legal framework likely to set working conditions, the professional environment and remuneration, and also determines the rights and obligations and standards to be respected for a socio-professional identity and a sense of fairness.

4.2.2 Motivation in the face of contractual job insecurity

The creation of a new status within the Ministry of Education constitutes a genuine organizational overhaul, a process of mutation that is a planned response to the pressures of a flexible environment (Bertron, 2021) and to the weaknesses observed prior to the reform. A new, more durable and more massive data set that has created interaction between people, information, decisions and resources. Its persistence will then force the Ministry to justify the duality of the rules governing the "careers" of some and others, to make them evolve towards even greater similarities, risking opening the way to strong resistance, which, in the current context, seems delicate.

Resistance can be defined as "a set of forces contributing to maintaining the stability of a system (integration into the public service), stemming either from an individual's personality characteristics, or from the social and cultural norms of groups" (Legendre, 2005, p. 1183).

Box on the ranking of verbatims on the perception of academy teacher-managers surveyed on contract recruitment - "A very unsuccessful system.

"....A very unsuccessful system, because it creates racism and discrimination between statutory and contract teachers in the same school, and this affects the teacher's psychology and productivity in the classroom, just as there is no financial stability" teacher 2.

".....Even though we are witnessing an acceleration in transfers in the public sector. The contractualization system increases precariousness in the education sector and, in some cases, contract teachers are subject to "the arbitrariness of certain school principals and provincial directors. "E5.

".... I'm in favor of economic regionalization, not regionalization at recruitment level, because this type of employment has serious consequences for teachers "E1

This context leads to stereotypes which, while they do exist, are certainly isolated cases, far from being representative of the majority of agents with regard to job security, cases where their contract has been interrupted and dismissal proceedings initiated by the administration, either because of serious misconduct or unjustified absences.

This feeling of lack of security has created resistance, confirmed by the rate of participation in the various protests and strikes, which exceeds 61% of contract teachers in our survey, who certify that they are taking part by joining the Coordination nationale des enseignants contractuels (National Coordination of Contract Teachers) according to the attached figure n 5

Figure n 5: the participation rate in various demonstrations and strikes:

Source: compiled by us.

The development of a two-tier system with segmentation between two groups of teachers has obvious consequences for motivation and morale, and resistance is often seen as a negative reaction that manifests itself as an attitude of refusal to support or implement the proposed change, and to eradicate it altogether. (next box). Box concerning the ranking of verbatims from academy head teachers questioned about contract recruitment. -Organizational fairness and professional equity.

".....I felt a kind of inferiority compared to statutory teachers and harassment from some principals," teacher1

"..... I work with all the responsibility and dedication, but nobody encourages you, except some hard-working students who appreciate that. The Ministry only cares about the success rate of the students". E2

".....We want equality and inclusion in the civil service, contractualization has been imposed on us" E3

".... Why is the supervisory ministry pushing teachers who are required to contract to take the vocational education exam solely through a class visit by the pedagogical inspector, knowing that this exam is the one that qualifies the teacher and recognizes his or her professional and pedagogical competence?" E3

".....Contractualization does not ensure the psychological stability of the teacher, which negatively affects the quality of teaching."

"Je what really bothers me is the Feeling of equality in the profession and not benefiting from the same rights as a civil servant "

During the first interviews, given the sensitivity of the subject, we were obliged to reassure the source subjects in order to gain their trust and gather the information we needed. In spite of this, discussions and conversations with these teachers led to greater spontaneity, and sometimes a comment from one respondent will provoke and positively stimulate the reaction of others to participate. This technique enabled us to triangulate the words of the different subjects and gain a deeper understanding of the facets of our study.

In the following box, we collected some responses from academy teacher-managers about their assessment of the contractual and regional recruitment system in terms of status, and Job Security was presented as follows:

".....It's a system that degrades teachers, while they don't feel secure. I don't agree with this type of recruitment, because there's a lot of inequality between teachers and less job security." teacher 2

"..... The system is unfair and unjust and contributes to the psychological and professional insecurity that affects the normal progress of studies. "E3

".....I'm afraid of being replaced by another teacher for no reason just because someone in charge didn't like my behavior, my refusal of a request or the excessive use of his or her authority. "E 4

"..... at any time, these contract teachers can be dismissed. This is what gives rise to a feeling of instability among these teachers, forced to live the precariousness of work with the State" union representative.

It was pointed out that the new development model defended 3 principles concerning teachers: moving towards a single status, mapping out a new career path and linking pay rises and promotions to performance.

Beyond the notion of reform that the Moroccan school system is undergoing, that of resistance is inherent in the implementation of transformations and many current mutations.

As soon as a job has been secured to escape unemployment, the laureates go on to demand equal treatment and, above all, integration into the civil service. They find support from the national coordination, ready to fight for parity and equity with their statutory counterparts, and sometimes from public opinion, despite the fact that they accepted different conditions of access to employment when they were recruited.

Sometimes, contract teachers and civil servant teachers join forces to demand their rights and block the operation of the entire system. In Senegal, for example, the amicale des enseignants volontaires was created, and later transformed into a trade union, demonstrating the kind of balance of power that can make governments back down. To do this, they use their main weapon: their mobilization (untimely strikes, threats to boycott exams).

Indeed, resistance can have an impact on implementation, job satisfaction and individual behavior.

5. Discussion

The research hypothesis that this contractualization process has an impact on the motivation of contract teachers is confirmed.

A large number of teachers saw it as a source of "discriminatory" demotivation, stigmatization and lack of involvement (CHARLES PAUVERT, 2002). Year after year, they continue to demand maximum rights, particularly as regards their integration into the civil service, which manifests itself in repeated strikes, absenteeism, insubordination, desertion of posts and boycott of service meetings.

The "motivation" paradigm of the teaching profession, articulated around multiple demands. This variable is a moderator of the relationship between managerial and organizational representations and teacher performance. (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Diagram "Causes of intrinsic non-motivation among teachers"

Source: Nvivo 10 software output

The survey results attest to the fact that, in the minds of teachers, the employment relationship revolves around a predefined pattern, the job for life, where the idea of a job that can be determined over time seems to contradict their explicit, specific expectations, responding more to a relational than a transactional logic, and where questions of job security take on particular importance.

On the other hand, theoretical propositions benefit from empirical support, in the sense that numerous studies highlight the links between high levels of staff motivation and long-term professional commitment. Uncertainty and job insecurity are one of the main motivations in the orientation of individual or organizational behaviors that were particularly noted during the focus groups and interviews. The questionnaire also reinforces this finding.

This is partly due to the fact that the data collected as part of this research reflect the experiences and perceptions that Moroccan contract teachers have of their working conditions and status. They perceive that they suffer from real organizational injustice due to this difference, and an imbalance of comparison between two similar categories working in the same organization. Feelings of inequity create an unfavorable perception of the organization, which can influence job dissatisfaction, lack of motivation and commitment to the job.

Referring back to contract theory, one of the major characteristics of a contract is its incompleteness, where one of the parties may seek to derive maximum benefit from the situation, to the detriment of the other (main) party's interests. The contractual approach to the firm has developed to overcome the limitations of the neoclassical approach by attempting to define the most efficient organizational form where the contractual relationship between principal and agent is balanced.

However, this process takes time, because reform is never a free act, and as we saw in the first chapter, it entails transaction costs at every stage of implementation. There is a risk that the players involved will move too quickly, and that the desire to apply a miraculous recipe, driven by the need to show results, will often tempt them to skip stages, resulting in misunderstandings and problems at every stage. It's essential to master one phase before moving on to the next.

6.Results

The validity of the concept was assessed using exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses. First, an exploratory factor analysis and a principal component analysis were performed. All question items were entered simultaneously, and items with cross-saturations below 0.40 were also removed. In the end, we obtained four distinct factors, as initially planned. Their eigenvalues were greater than 1.0. Cronbach's α -coefficient was applied to test the reliability of the constructs.

The reliability of the overall constructs of work motivation and organizational commitment, was satisfactory with $\alpha > 0.70$ indicating acceptable internal consistency.

The possibility of factoring the data was demonstrated by the value of the KMO index, which was above the reference threshold selected, and by a strong significance of 0.797,

We have a single eigenvalue greater than 1, allowing us to retain a single factor that returns 64,022% of the total information.

Next, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was applied on the basis of the EFA results, using Amos 22. The fit indices of the final model using first-order constructs showed satisfactory levels ($\chi^2 = 0.131$; Ddl. =2; $\chi^2/d.f. = 0.065$; GFI = 0.999; CFI = 0.995 RMR = 0.005 and RMSEA = 0.010). The standardized chi-square of 1.430 was below the maximum value of 3.0

The research hypothesis that this contractualization process has a negative impact on the motivation of contract teachers is confirmed.

A large number of teachers saw it as a source of "discriminatory" demotivation and stigmatization, and year after year they continue to demand maximum rights, particularly as regards their integration into the civil service, which manifests itself in repeated strikes, absenteeism, and insubordination, desertion of posts and boycott of service meetings.

The results of the survey attest to the fact that, in the minds of teachers, the employment relationship revolves around a predefined pattern, the job for life, where the idea of a job that can be determined over time seems to contradict their explicit, specific expectations, responding more to a relational than a transactional logic, and where questions linked to job security take on particular importance.

On the other hand, theoretical propositions benefit from empirical support, in the sense that numerous studies highlight the links between high levels of staff motivation and professional commitment. Uncertainty and job insecurity are one of the main de-motivators in the orientation of individual or organizational behaviors that were particularly noted during the interviews. The questionnaire also reinforces this finding.

Moroccan contract teachers' perceptions of their working conditions and status represent an interesting process to take into account in order to gain a better understanding of teachers' well-being and malaise, as well as their demands. The resulting dosages give rise to new reactions to the system.

They perceive that they are suffering from real organizational injustice due to this difference, and from an imbalance of comparison between two similar categories working in the same organization. Feelings of inequity create an unfavorable perception of This can have an impact on job dissatisfaction, lack of motivation and commitment to the job.

Referring back to contract theory, one of the major characteristics of the contract is its incompleteness, where one of the parties may seek to derive maximum benefit from the situation,

Absenteeism, lack of motivation and weak disciplinary procedures the level of commitment shown by contract staff is higher than that of permanent staff	Absenteeism, lack of motivation and weak disciplinary procedures the level of commitment shown by contract staff is higher than that of permanent staff
Monitoring and managing permanent staff is difficult, given the age pyramid close to retirement.	as the population of contract employees is younger and therefore in better health than that of civil servants, strengthen all forms of work incentives and improve the quality of life of contract employees.

Conclusion

The aim of our study was to examine the relationship between recruitment by contact and motivation, and an in-depth explanation of the causes of teachers' favorable or unfavorable behaviors. Initially, we studied forms of motivation by means of a literature review that synthesized all studies dealing with the concepts specific to our research (equity and psychological contract theory). Then, on an empirical level, we were able to identify a result according to which affective commitment is lower (or even significantly lower) among contract teachers who seek equitable behaviours.

The theory of psychological contracting and fairness has served as a foundation for explaining the exchange reactions that exist between agents and organizations. The psychological contract aims to understand and analyze the dynamics of this relationship, as well as the way in which the exchange is set up and evolves over time, and equity theory, explains how decisions perceived as unfair, the parties tend, under certain conditions, to modify their behavior due to this aversion to inequity, so as to regain an equilibrium perceived as fair.

The research hypothesis that this contractualisation process has a negative impact on teacher motivation is confirmed.

The survey results confirm that the theoretical proposals are supported by empirical evidence, with numerous studies highlighting the links between high levels of staff motivation and professional commitment. Uncertainty and job insecurity are key factors influencing individual and organisational behaviour, which were particularly evident during the interviews. Contractualisation does not appear to be compatible with the need for job security and stability.

This is why teachers' motivation was low and correlated with negative emotions generated by the need for a stable status. According to them, the employment relationship is based on a predefined model of stable and permanent employment, or the idea of a contract whose duration seems to contradict their explicit expectations, which are based on a rational logic where issues of job security take on particular importance.

Our results also show that these teachers' motivations moderate the relationship between their psychological contract and their affective commitment to the organization.

The pressure exerted by repeated teachers' strikes and their reluctant behaviour was an obstacle to the implementation of the contract in the public sector, which prompted the ministry to opt for regional recruitment and also demonstrates the need to consider motivation as an important variable in the employment relationship in HRM.

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